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THE NEXUS BETWEEN CORRUPTION AND IMPEACHMENT OF GOVERNORS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Corruption in Nigeria has become a persistent national embarrassment, manifesting in acts of dishonesty, lack of accountability, and the misappropriation of public resources. Its pervasiveness impedes national development and poses a threat to both internal stability and global security. In response, democratic systems globally including Nigeria have institutionalised impeachment as a mechanism for removing errant public officials. Sections 143 and 188 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria provide legal backing for the removal of presidents, vice presidents, governors, and deputy governors. This study examines the nexus between the impeachment of state governors and allegations of corruption within Nigeria's Fourth Republic. The work interrogates whether impeachment proceedings genuinely reflect anti-corruption efforts or serve as instruments of political witch-hunting. Anchored on the Social Contract Theory, the study views the constitution as a binding agreement between the government and the governed, where violations, including corruption, attract sanctions such as impeachment. A qualitative methodology was adopted, sourcing data from newspapers, journals, books, and credible internet publications. These were subjected to content analysis to trace the underlying motivations, political manoeuvres, and legal interpretations of impeachment cases. The paper reveals that while impeachment is constitutionally justified in cases of gross misconduct, its application in Nigeria is often manipulated for political ends. The study concludes that unless political interference is curtailed and due process strictly followed, impeachment will remain a tool of vendetta rather than a safeguard of public accountability.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption remains one of the most persistent threats to political stability, good governance, and sustainable development in Nigeria. It has

become a deeply entrenched phenomenon, transcending historical periods from colonial rule to the present democratic era. As a systemic issue, corruption infiltrates virtually all sectors of

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public life; undermining state capacity, eroding public trust, distorting institutional processes, and inhibiting equitable development. The normalization of corrupt practices in Nigeria, particularly among public officeholders, has contributed significantly to the fragility of democratic institutions and the misallocation of public resources (Akinrinade & Olarinmoye, 2012).

To curb this endemic problem, Nigeria has adopted a range of legal and political mechanisms. One of such mechanism is impeachment, a constitutional process intended to remove elected public officials, especially executive governors found guilty of gross misconduct or violations of the constitution. It is rooted in the presidential model borrowed from the United States, impeachment was introduced into Nigeria's political-legal framework during the short-lived Second Republic. This process gained prominence following the adoption of the 1999 Constitution, which, under Section 308, grants broad immunity to sitting executive officers from civil or criminal proceedings. The impeachment clause was thus included to serve as a vital accountability tool, balancing executive immunity with a means to sanction egregious misconduct (Oni, 2013).

Since the inception of Nigeria's Fourth Republic on May 29, 1999, successive administrations have enacted many anti-corruption initiatives. During President Olusegun Obasanjo's

administration, essential entities like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) were created to investigate and punish corrupt individuals. Reforms in the public sector, including the monetisation policy and public procurement improvements, were enacted to reduce bureaucratic inefficiency and enhance accountability.

Further reforms emerged during the Jonathan administration, notably the Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS), which revealed thousands of ghost workers and curtailed payroll fraud. The Treasury Single Account (TSA), though conceptualized under Jonathan, was fully enforced under President Muhammadu Buhari's government to consolidate federal revenue and reduce leakages in public finance (Okonjo-Iweala, 2018).

Despite these measures, corruption remains pervasive. Several governors have been subjected to impeachment processes under allegations of corruption. However, most impeachments have either been overturned by the judiciary or marred by accusations of political vendettas and procedural irregularities. The impeachment of Governor Diepreye Alamiyeseigha of Bayelsa State stands out, as he legally contested his removal without success. Other cases suggest that beyond corruption, political motivations, party dynamics, and elite rivalries often drive

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impeachment proceedings (Albert, 2005; Alalibo, 2018).

This study, therefore, interrogates the complex relationship between corruption and the impeachment of governors in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. It aims to uncover the underlying motivations behind impeachments: Are they truly driven by a commitment to public accountability, or are they tools for political retribution? Who are the principal actors in these processes, and to what extent are they influenced by coercion, inducement, or patronage politics? These questions are critical in evaluating whether impeachment in Nigeria functions as an anti-corruption mechanism or merely a political instrument.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

2.1 The Concept of Corruption

Corruption in its simplest form, is the abuse of entrusted power for private gain. This abuse manifests in various ways, including bribery, embezzlement, nepotism, and the diversion of public funds or assets. The Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Act (ICPC Act, 2000) defines corruption as the abuse of office for personal gain, whether through the solicitation, acceptance, or offering of bribes to circumvent due process. The ICPC notes that public office is abused not only when a public official accepts bribes but also when private agents offer them to gain unfair advantage (ICPC Act, 2002). Agbu reinforces this position by

asserting that corruption extends beyond bribery to include nepotism, patronage, and even theft of state assets in the absence of direct monetary exchange (Agbu, 2003).

Corruption involves behavior that deviates from established ethical norms and the legal expectations of public trust. It can be perpetrated by anyone elected, appointed, or even private individuals so long as the act is executed for personal interest at the expense of the collective good. In this way, corruption becomes a betrayal of public trust and an affront to governance structures designed to serve the populace (Okojie & Momoh, 2005).

Nigeria's struggle with corruption has been persistent and systemic. Seteolu identifies corruption as a significant barrier to Nigeria's national development, citing manifestations such as bribery, embezzlement, favoritism, advance fee fraud (419), and money laundering (Seteolu, 2004). These practices have entrenched themselves so deeply into Nigeria's social fabric that terms like "sorting," "settlementocracy," "kleptocracy," and "contractocracy" have become part of the country's lexicon, reflecting how normalized corrupt practices have become over time (Transparency International, 2005).

Statistical and anecdotal evidence both point to the pervasiveness of corruption in Nigeria. For instance, a report from the Office of the Auditor-General for the Federation in 2020 disclosed

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government contract fraud and procurement violations worth nearly \$117 million in that year alone (Office of the Auditor General of the Federation, 2024). High-profile international cases further highlight the global footprint of Nigeria's corruption challenges. These include the Glencore bribery scandal, in which over \$52 million in bribes were paid to intermediaries in Nigeria (U.S. Department of Justice, 2022; Judiciary of England and Wales, 2022), and the prosecution of former governor James Ibori, whose case involved the laundering of over \$80 million (Crown Prosecution Service, 2023).

The impact of corruption is not only financial but deeply structural. The Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) revealed the 2012 embezzlement of \$2.1 billion in pension funds allocated to retired police officers, highlighting how systemic corruption undermines the welfare of even the most vulnerable citizens (EFCC, 2022). Despite the existence of multiple anti-corruption bodies and reforms from the War Against Indiscipline (WAI) in the 1980s to the establishment of the EFCC in 2002 corruption continues to thrive due to a culture of impunity and weak institutional enforcement (EFCC, 2002; ICPC, 2006).

The social consequences of corruption are equally alarming. According to UNODC and Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics, both petty and grand corruption have eroded public trust, weakened institutions, and hindered

service delivery, forcing citizens to rely on informal and exploitative coping mechanisms (UNODC & NBS, 2024). This entrenched culture of corruption perpetuates a vicious cycle of underdevelopment, inequality, and lawlessness. Public opinion data suggest that Nigerians overwhelmingly disapprove of corruption. Survey results from NOIPolls and research by Chatham House show that most Nigerians morally oppose corrupt practices and view anti-corruption reforms as essential to national progress (Hoffmann & Patel, 2022; NOIPolls, 2024). Nevertheless, in everyday life, corruption is often perceived as a necessary evil—a means of navigating bureaucratic inefficiencies and securing access to services in a dysfunctional system. As Mishra argues, in such contexts, the perception persists that "corruption is the price for getting things done," especially where accountability is absent and integrity is penalized (Mishra, 2005).

It is therefore clear that corruption in Nigeria is not merely a legal or administrative problem but a deeply embedded cultural and political issue. It thrives in weak institutions, flourishes under political patronage, and is normalized through societal complicity and survivalist mentalities. To address it effectively, Nigeria requires not only stronger enforcement mechanisms but also a reorientation of societal values and the redefinition of public service as a trust, not a privilege.

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CONCEPT OF IMPEACHMENT

Impeachment is a constitutional process used to formally accuse and potentially remove a public official from office due to misconduct. In the Nigerian context, it refers primarily to the removal of elected officials such as the President, Vice President, Governors, and Deputy Governors. While the term “impeachment” is not explicitly stated in Sections 143 and 188 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, these sections clearly outline the process for removing the aforementioned officeholders. Other references to impeachment are found in Sections 84, 124, 146, and 191, which relate to pensions and the transfer of executive functions upon removal. Thus, for the purpose of this study, impeachment will be understood strictly as the constitutional process of removing top executive officeholders in Nigeria (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999; Alalibo, 2018).

Michael Gerhardt, a commentator during the impeachment of U.S. President Bill Clinton, defined impeachment in operational terms as an inherently political mechanism designed to address political crises without the need for judicial or executive approval. It is fundamentally a legislative tool for terminating the tenure of an elected official before its natural expiration (Arinze, Eze, & Nwaeze, 2016). According to Okunade and Muhammed (2014), impeachment serves as a constitutional check on executive overreach. However, in Nigeria, this

tool has often been misused and politicized, particularly since the nation’s return to democratic rule in 1999.

Several impeachment cases in Nigeria have raised concerns over the abuse of this constitutional provision. Observers have noted that many impeachments are not the result of proven “gross misconduct,” as constitutionally required, but are instead politically motivated, often driven by rival parties or internal party factions (Okunade & Mohammed, 2014). For instance, allegations were made during the 2014 political crisis that the ruling People’s Democratic Party (PDP) targeted governors from the opposition All Progressives Congress (APC) for removal. These accusations, although denied by the presidency, were viewed by many as credible, especially given the timing and coordination of the impeachment attempts (Okunade & Mohammed, 2014; Lawal, 2014).

Former military head of state Muhammadu Buhari described these politically induced impeachments as a significant threat to Nigeria’s fragile democracy (Kumolu, 2014). Unlike the United States, where impeachment is sparingly used and reserved for severe infractions—only 19 successful impeachment processes out of 64 attempts since 1789 Nigeria’s legislature has invoked impeachment more frequently and with less restraint (Kargbo, 2014). Since 1999, several high-profile Nigerian governors have been impeached, including Diepreye Alamieyeseigha

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(Bayelsa), Ayo Fayose (Ekiti), Joshua Dariye (Plateau), Murtala Nyaku (Adamawa) and Rashidi Ladoja (Oyo), along with multiple deputy governors across various states.

Critics argue that Nigeria's legislature often fabricates charges of “gross misconduct” to justify removals that serve political ends. Rather than ensuring accountability, the impeachment process has been manipulated as a weapon for settling personal or party-related scores (Obi, 2014; Mahmud, 2014). This trend undermines democratic governance and erodes public trust in the rule of law. Onah (2014) laments the frequent misuse of impeachment, warning that it endangers the business of governance and contributes to instability within the political system.

The concept of impeachment in Nigeria has deviated from its intended constitutional purpose. What should be a legal and ethical tool for ensuring accountability has instead become a politically charged instrument, often deployed for expediency. The challenge remains for Nigeria's democratic institutions to reassert the integrity of this process and align it more closely with its foundational legal and democratic principles.

EXECUTIVE IMMUNITY AND ACCOUNTABILITY

Executive immunity in Nigeria refers to the legal protection afforded to sitting executive officeholders, namely: the President, Vice

President, Governors, and Deputy Governors. It shields them from civil and criminal proceedings while in office. This immunity is constitutionally entrenched in Section 308 of the 1999 Constitution, which states, “Notwithstanding anything to the contrary... no criminal proceeding or civil proceeding shall be instituted or continued against the President, the Vice-President, the Governor or Deputy Governor...” until after they leave office. This provision is intended to ensure that incumbents can perform their duties without undue distraction or frivolous litigation (Sylvester, 2020).

However, this constitutionally enshrined protection often paradoxically undermines the principle of accountability. Scholars including Sambo (2022) argue that Section 308 effectively impedes the fight against corruption by granting executives a temporary license to shield misconduct, making it exceedingly difficult to hold them to account for corruption while in office. This disconnect between legal immunity and ethical accountability raises serious governance concerns. As one reform advocate points out, “the clause should not cover fraud, corruption and vindictive tendencies in government” (Agbo, Saredau, & Dafiell, 2024). Empirical research highlights this contradiction. For example, Sambo's analysis of executives investigated for corruption during their term demonstrates that they frequently escape

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accountability due to immunity, enabling unethical behavior in the interim (Sambo, 2022). A mathematical simulation further shows that removing Section 308 would likely reduce corruption by curbing the “corruption reproduction ratio” among immunized officeholders (Gweryina, Kura, & Okwu, 2019).

Defenders of the clause argue that it prevents frivolous lawsuits that could paralyze governance (Emelife & Obi, 2024). Indeed, in some jurisdictions, immunity allows leaders to focus on crisis management and governance without the fear of court actions. Yet even experts sympathetic to immunity acknowledge that those accused of corruption must face justice if only after their term ends with reasonable speed, before evidence deteriorates or witnesses disappear (Okeke & Okeke, 2015). In practice, Section 308 fosters a climate of impunity. Similarly, the Shield of immunity often delays justice to a point where accountability becomes a symbolic gesture rather than a real deterrent.

Nigeria’s framework for executive immunity presents a significant accountability paradox. While protecting officeholders from petty litigation is an understandable goal, the breadth and duration of this immunity as currently implemented creates space for major malfeasance to go unchecked. Many scholars advocate for reform, such as narrowing the scope of immunity to exclude corruption and fraud or instituting post-term legal thresholds for prompt

prosecution. These reforms would help align executive privilege with democratic accountability.

THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVE

The Social Contract Theory remains a cornerstone in political philosophy, offering insights into the legitimacy of political power and the reciprocal responsibilities between a government and its citizens. At its core, the theory posits that individuals, through either implicit or explicit consent, agree to relinquish certain personal liberties in exchange for the protection of their fundamental rights and the preservation of societal order. This conceptual framework provides a foundational understanding of the ethical and political ties that bind the governed to their governors.

Thomas Hobbes was one of the earliest thinkers to formally articulate the theory in his influential 1651 work, *Leviathan*. He portrayed the natural state of humanity as chaotic and violent—describing life without governance as “solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short” (Hobbes, 1651/2012). According to Hobbes, individuals collectively established a sovereign power to avoid this state of anarchy, ensuring peace and legal order. In contrast, John Locke, in his *Two Treatises of Government* (1689), reoriented the theory toward natural rights, arguing that political authority must be derived from the obligation to safeguard life, liberty, and property. Locke further contended that any government

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that violates these rights could be justifiably overthrown (Locke, 1689/1988). Jean-Jacques Rousseau advanced the discourse in *The Social Contract* (1762), emphasizing that genuine political legitimacy arises from the general will of the populace (Rousseau, 1762/2002). These classical thinkers collectively laid the ideological foundation for democratic governance and constitutionalism.

The 20th century witnessed a revival of the theory, notably by John Rawls in *A Theory of Justice* (1971). Rawls introduced the notion of the “original position,” a hypothetical scenario in which rational individuals, unaware of their social or economic status (“the veil of ignorance”), would choose principles of justice that guarantee fairness and equity for all. His reformulation sparked renewed interest in the social contract as a tool for evaluating public policy and social institutions (Rawls, 1971). Building on this tradition, other scholars have expanded or critiqued the theory. David Gauthier, for example, developed a neo-Hobbesian variant in *Morals by Agreement* (1986), arguing that rational self-interest could justify cooperative moral behavior. Carole Pateman, in *The Sexual Contract* (1988), exposed the patriarchal underpinnings of classical contract theories, while Charles Mills' *The Racial Contract* (1997) revealed how traditional formulations systematically excluded non-white groups. These reinterpretations

underscore the theory's adaptability and relevance in addressing issues of justice, inclusion, and state authority.

Central tenets of the Social Contract Theory include the idea that political legitimacy stems from the consent of the governed, that public institutions should prioritize the common good, and that leaders must be held accountable to prevent abuses of power. The theory also affirms the right of citizens to resist or remove leaders who breach the contract through corruption, oppression, or failure to ensure justice.

This framework directly informs the current study, which explores the relationship between corruption and the impeachment of executive governors in Nigeria's Fourth Republic. Nigeria's constitutional democracy is grounded in a social contract enshrined in the 1999 Constitution, particularly in Sections 143 and 188, which provide the legal grounds for impeaching elected officials on the basis of gross misconduct. When public officials engage in corrupt practices, they violate this implicit agreement with the electorate. Impeachment, in this context, functions as a constitutional remedy to reestablish public trust and uphold the rule of law.

POWERS AND ROLES OF LEGISLATURE IN DEMOCRACY

The legislative power in Nigeria is enshrined in Chapter 4, Section 5, and the Legislative Lists under the second schedule of the 1999

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Constitution. The National Assembly has the exclusive ability to execute certain delineated powers, including the establishment of new states and local government districts. Section 4(1) confers legislative competence to the National Assembly regarding the Federal Republic of Nigeria. This jurisdiction encompasses the adoption of laws aimed for preserving the federation's peace, order, and good governance about any matter on the exclusive legislative list. Section 4(7) grants state legislatures control over any issue on the concurrent list, any explicitly assigned state responsibility, and any matter not specifically allocated to either the federal or state governments, including all items on the residual list.

Nwabueze (2007) asserts that the legislature is a definitive indicator of a nation's sovereignty, a gauge of its status as a state, and the primary source of the power exercised by the executive in governmental functions. The Constitution, by bestowing lawmaking authority onto the institution, entrusts this power to the entity empowered to formulate laws via legislation and provide enforceable directives to the society. The legislative branch is therefore considered the primary source of constitutional power, followed by the executive and judiciary branches in SS5 and SS6, respectively. Nwabueze notes that the constitutional hierarchy is skewed because the leaders of the legislature—the president of the

Senate, the speaker of the House of Representatives, and the speakers of the State Houses of Assembly—do not possess the status of first citizen accorded to the president at the federal level or governors at the state level. Consequently, despite the legislature possessing the constitutionally supreme authority, its leadership does not assume the position of chief executive. The legislative power in Nigeria is enshrined in Chapter 4, Section 5, and the Legislative Lists in the second schedule of the 1999 Constitution. The National Assembly has the unique power to execute certain stated powers, including the establishment of new states and local government districts. Section 4(1) confers legislative competence to the National Assembly of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. This jurisdiction include the adoption of laws aimed for preserving the federation's peace, order, and good governance over any matter on the exclusive legislative list.

Conversely, Subsection 4(7) grants state legislatures power over all matters on the concurrent list, any specifically assigned state responsibilities, and any topics not explicitly allocated to either the federal or state governments, namely those on the residual list. Nwabueze (2007) asserts that the legislature is a definitive indicator of a nation's sovereignty, a gauge of its status as a state, and the primary source of the power exercised by the executive in governmental functions. The Constitution

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IMPEACHED EXECUTIVES IN NIGERIA'S FOURTH REPUBLIC: INTRIGUES AND UNDERCURRENTS

At the beginning of Nigeria's Fourth Republic in 1999, under the administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo's first term (1999–2003), no sitting governor was removed from office, except for the deputy governor of Abia State, Senator Enyinnaya Abaribe. However, between 2003 and 2007, Nigeria experienced a sudden wave of gubernatorial impeachments, an era commonly referred to as the "impeachment gale" in the country's political discourse, though Governor

Murtala Nyako of Adamawa was impeached under President Goodluck Jonathan's Administration in 2014. This wave started with the case of the late Chief Diepreye Solomon Peter Alamiyeseigha, then Governor of Bayelsa State. His ordeal began following his arrest in London by the Metropolitan Police on allegations of money laundering. This triggered a petition from a non-governmental organization alleging corruption and financial crimes.

Subsequently, on November 23, 2005, the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) summoned members of the Bayelsa State House of Assembly to its Lagos office to brief them on the governor's alleged misconduct and illicit accumulation of wealth amounting to over ₦1.7 billion. Under intense pressure, 17 out of the 24 legislators signed and executed the impeachment proceedings on December 9, 2005. Reports suggest that the lawmakers were compelled to endorse the impeachment notice at the EFCC's Lagos office before returning to Yenagoa to complete the process, suggesting they acted under coercion (Kayode, 2014). Alamiyeseigha challenged the impeachment in court but was unsuccessful. He was convicted, imprisoned, later released, and granted a presidential pardon. He eventually died amid speculations linked to a possible extradition to the UK over the same charges.

By January 2006, the political heat turned to Senator Rashidi Ladoja, the Governor of Oyo

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State at the time. His impeachment was widely seen as politically motivated and orchestrated with backing from the federal government. Ladoja had fallen out of favor with President Obasanjo due to his opposition to the president's third-term ambition and his alliance with Vice President Atiku Abubakar. Only 18 members of the Oyo State House of Assembly initiated the impeachment, well below the constitutionally required threshold of 22. The process was led by local power broker Lamidi Adedibu and was based on the findings of a controversial six-member panel (instead of the constitutionally mandated seven) that accused Ladoja of misappropriating state funds. On December 7, 2006, the Supreme Court nullified the impeachment, reinforcing the perception that it was carried out through undemocratic means (Ozekhome, 2006; Kargbo & Awom, 2014).

A similar scenario played out in Plateau State, where Governor Joshua Dariye was impeached on November 13, 2006. In this case, just six out of 24 lawmakers carried out the impeachment with federal backing, blatantly disregarding constitutional requirements. Dariye was accused of operating foreign bank accounts and owning undeclared foreign assets. After prolonged legal battles, he was reinstated in May 2007 before the expiration of his tenure, following court rulings that the impeachment lacked legal merit (Olamide, 2014; Awom, 2014).

In Ekiti State, Governor Ayodele Fayose faced both political opposition and a media spectacle. Once a close ally of Obasanjo, Fayose reportedly lost favor due to his support for Atiku Abubakar. The EFCC moved against him with allegations involving the embezzlement of ₦1.2 billion linked to a poultry project. On October 6, 2006, both Fayose and his deputy, Mrs. Biodun Olujimi, were impeached. However, Obasanjo had only intended for Fayose to be removed. The Assembly's defiance in also removing Olujimi, who later became a senator, led to the declaration of a state of emergency in the state. On October 19, 2006, Brigadier General Adetunji Olurin (rtd) was appointed as the sole administrator of Ekiti State (Kumolu, 2014; Olumide, 2014). Fayose was later reinstated after a court found that the impeachment process was flawed and unconstitutional.

Anambra State's Peter Obi also fell victim to politically charged impeachment. He assumed office after the Supreme Court ruled that he was the rightful winner of the 2003 election, which had initially been awarded to Dr. Chris Ngige of the PDP. Obi, who ran under the All Progressives Grand Alliance (APGA), found himself at odds with a PDP-dominated House of Assembly. During a visit by President Obasanjo, Obi was warned that he would not be supported for re-election unless he defected to the PDP. True to that threat, he was impeached on November 2, 2006, only seven months into office, for alleged

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misconduct. Courts later nullified the impeachment and reinstated him, citing the illegality of the process (Kumolu, 2014; Awom, 2014; Baiyewu, 2014).

In 2014, Governor Murtala Nyako of Adamawa State became another target of impeachment. A retired Vice Admiral and former Chief of Naval Staff, Nyako defected from the PDP to the APC and publicly accused then-President Goodluck Jonathan of committing genocide in the North in a memo to the Northern Governors Forum. His relationship with the State Assembly deteriorated over party-related tensions. The legislature, with apparent support from the presidency, accused him of financial mismanagement dating back to 2007. He was impeached on July 15, 2014 (Agbamuche, 2014). After fleeing Nigeria, he returned post-2015 Presidential Election following President Muhammadu Buhari's electoral victory and pursued legal action to nullify his removal. The Supreme Court eventually ruled in 2016 that his impeachment was unconstitutional due to procedural flaws. However, the court denied his reinstatement on the grounds that his tenure had already lapsed as of February 7, 2016 (NWLR, Pt. 1562, 2017).

AN OVERVIEW OF CORRUPTION AND IMPEACHMENT OF GOVERNORS IN NIGERIA'S FOURTH REPUBLIC

Impeachment is a political process designed to prevent executive misconduct and enforce

accountability among governmental entities. Alalibo (2018) states that it is the constitutional process for the removal of an incumbent chief executive in cases of emergency. The impetus for its implementation is to ensure that those who exhibit substantial misconduct do not remain in the government. Moreover, impeachment functions as a democratic safeguard that enhances the rule of law, upholds individual rights, ensures due process, and fosters responsibility and monitoring. The grounds for impeachment are delineated in the national constitutions; the United States Constitution, Article II, Section 4, cites treason, bribery, or high crimes and misdemeanours, while the 1987 Constitution of the Philippines specifies culpable violation of the Constitution, treason, bribery, graft and corruption, other high crimes, or betrayal of public trust. Nigeria, 1999 is predicated on a broader term, gross misconduct. Notwithstanding this nomenclature, impeachment continues to serve as a legislative mechanism for the removal of government officials who have been formally charged with high crimes or significant misconduct (Lipset, 1995).

Notwithstanding this authority, impeachment is not designed to rectify all types of misconduct or inadequacy, serve as political retribution, or address trivial allegations. In Nigeria, the assertions must be substantial or startling. In *Inakoju v. Adeleke*, His Lordship Niki Tobi

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enumerates the following as sufficiently grave: interference with the constitutional functions of the legislature and judiciary through the exercise of overtly unconstitutional executive power; misuse of fiscal provisions of the Constitution; violation of the Code of Conduct for Public Officers; disregard and infringement of Chapter IV of the Constitution regarding fundamental rights; and interference with Local Government funds.

Beyond the multitude of offences often cited in impeachment proceedings, the process in Nigeria is frequently likened to a man with a fractured leg no matter how well it is treated by the finest surgeons, it rarely returns to full strength. An impeached governor or deputy governor, in most cases, will not sit back passively while the administration responsible for their removal continues to govern. Such individuals, alongside their political allies, often work actively to undermine the government, seeking to retaliate or regain relevance.

It is widely acknowledged within Nigeria's political environment that bribery is commonly used as a tool to influence state assembly members. These legislators are frequently accused of accepting inducements from governors to remove deputy governors, speakers, or other principal officers. Conversely, there are claims that governors themselves become victims of such bribes. A notable example involved the All Progressives Congress (APC),

which alleged that lawmakers in Adamawa State received \$300,000 each to support the impeachment of Governor Murtala Nyako (Mohammed, 2014). While this might appear speculative, the historical record supports the assertion that financial incentives often drive impeachment actions in Nigeria (Mohammed, 2014). When funds meant for development projects are instead diverted to gratify the personal interests of corrupt politicians, the very foundation of democracy is threatened. Following the impeachment of Governor Ayodele Fayose in Ekiti State, public sentiment was so disillusioned that there were renewed calls for military intervention a dangerous signal for democratic survival (Sagey, 2010).

The frequent use of impeachment as a political weapon has significantly eroded its constitutional sanctity. Instead of serving as a legitimate check on executive excesses, impeachment has increasingly become a strategic device used to eliminate political opposition. This abuse undermines democratic values and fosters a climate of instability, thereby weakening democratic consolidation (Ogundiya, 2007; Agbude, 2013). Many deputy governors have been removed from office simply because they dared to express ambitions of succeeding their governors. One of the most prominent instances of this trend was the political showdown between former President Olusegun Obasanjo and his then Vice President, Atiku

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Abubakar. Atiku's decision to contest the presidency while Obasanjo was allegedly pursuing a third term led to his suspension from the People's Democratic Party (PDP) and attempts to force him out of office. The Supreme Court eventually ruled in Atiku's favor, preserving his position (Olumide, 2005).

A similar political motivation was apparent in the case of Governor Murtala Nyako of Adamawa State. After defecting from the PDP to the APC, Nyako became a vocal critic of President Goodluck Jonathan's administration. His swift impeachment raised suspicions about federal interference. Observers noted that the move was likely part of a broader strategy by the presidency to weaken the opposition by reclaiming APC-held states, particularly those previously under PDP control, ahead of the 2015 general elections (Awon, 2014; Onah, 2014; Obi, 2014). Although Nigeria's constitution allows for the removal of a governor based on "gross misconduct," it fails to precisely define what the term entails. This ambiguity gives legislators excessive discretion to categorize almost any executive action as misconduct. As a result, impeachment can be triggered by minor administrative missteps or disagreements, rather than actual violations of law.

This broad interpretation of "gross misconduct" serves the interests of political actors seeking to punish dissenters or eliminate rivals. During Obasanjo's tenure, for example, impeachment

was widely used against governors and deputies who opposed his controversial third-term bid (Deji, 2014; Nwabueze, 2007). A review of impeachment cases since the adoption of the 1999 Constitution shows that deputy governors have suffered the highest number of removals. This trend is linked to the structural weakness of the office itself. While the deputy governor is constitutionally recognized, the role lacks clearly defined powers or responsibilities. Often appointed as running mates based on political compromise, deputies are at the mercy of governors who may seek to remove them if tensions arise.

Even when a deputy governor is imposed on the governor by influential political stakeholders, a smooth working relationship is not guaranteed. Regardless of their competence or intentions, deputy governors often find themselves with limited influence in the administration. Section 186 of the 1999 Constitution provides for the office but does not assign any inherent powers; instead, it leaves the allocation of duties to the discretion of the governor. This lack of statutory authority makes deputies particularly vulnerable to impeachment, often without substantial evidence of wrongdoing. Given these realities, it is reasonable to argue that many impeachments, especially those carried out during the Fourth Republic, have been politically engineered rather than rooted in genuine accountability or corruption. The pattern reflects a broader misuse

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of constitutional provisions for self-serving ends, casting a shadow over Nigeria's democratic development.

CONCLUSION

The impeachment process, while constitutionally grounded, remains deeply political in nature, especially within the context of Nigeria's Fourth Republic. As this study has shown, impeachment is not merely a legal tool for upholding accountability, but often a political weapon susceptible to manipulation and abuse. The intersection of corruption and impeachment reveals a troubling trend: while impeachment ought to function as a constitutional mechanism to check executive excesses and uphold democratic accountability, it is often wielded as a tool of political vendetta, driven by power struggles rather than genuine concern for governance or the rule of law. The undefined nature of the term "gross misconduct" in Section 188 of the 1999 Constitution leaves ample room for subjective interpretation, making impeachment vulnerable to political exploitation. As demonstrated in the cases of several impeached governors during President Obasanjo's and one in President Goodluck Jonathan's tenure, the legal process has often been overshadowed by executive interference, legislative partisanship, and judicial reversals. While corruption undeniably undermines the moral and functional legitimacy of governance, using impeachment as a selective punishment

tool without due process erodes public trust in democratic institutions. Therefore, a recalibration of Nigeria's constitutional and political approach to executive accountability is urgently needed not only to preserve the sanctity of the rule of law but to safeguard the integrity of Nigeria's democratic framework.

RECOMMENDATIONS

i. Clear Definition of "Gross Misconduct":

The Nigerian Constitution should be amended to provide an unambiguous and detailed definition of "gross misconduct", though partially explained in Justice Niki Tobi's Supreme Court Judgement, it does not sufficiently deal with the proper definition of the complete meaning of the phrase- gross misconduct. This will curtail arbitrary interpretations and ensure that only clearly established offenses, particularly those relating to corruption, abuse of office, and ethical violations, qualify as grounds for impeachment.

ii. Strengthening Due Process Mechanisms:

Legislative bodies must strictly adhere to the procedural requirements laid out in Section 188(1–9) of the 1999 Constitution. The judiciary, civil society, and constitutional oversight bodies should ensure compliance with these steps to prevent impeachment from being overturned due to technical irregularities.

iii. Depoliticization of the Impeachment Process:

Efforts should be made to insulate the impeachment process from partisan interference. Political parties and the presidency

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must refrain from orchestrating or influencing legislative decisions regarding impeachment. This can be supported by reinforcing institutional independence and promoting political maturity among lawmakers.

iv. Enhanced Role of Civil Society and Media: Civil society organizations, the media, and legal advocacy groups must play an active role in scrutinizing impeachment proceedings to ensure transparency, objectivity, and adherence to constitutional norms. Public engagement can serve as a deterrent against politically motivated impeachments.

v. Establishment of a Constitutional Interpretation Committee: A neutral and independent body should be established to provide binding interpretations of ambiguous constitutional terms such as “gross misconduct.” This committee could include representatives from the judiciary, legislature, civil society, and academia.

vi. Judicial Safeguards for Fair Trials: Impeached officials must be guaranteed the right to a fair hearing throughout the impeachment process. The role of judicial panels should be emphasized, and their independence ensured to objectively assess allegations against public officials.

vii. Post-Impeachment Legal Accountability: To balance executive

immunity and accountability, impeached officials found guilty of corruption or constitutional violations should face post-office prosecution. Legal mechanisms should be expedited to avoid evidence decay or political shielding after tenure expiration.

viii. Capacity Building for Legislators: Periodic training and constitutional literacy programs should be introduced for legislators, especially those at the state level, to deepen their understanding of impeachment procedures, ethical standards, and their role in upholding democratic values.

ix. Constitutional Review to Limit Abuse of Section 308: Section 308, which grants executive immunity, should be reviewed to exclude corruption-related offenses. This would ensure that allegations of financial impropriety can be investigated and prosecuted even while the official remains in office, thus deterring impunity.

x. Promotion of Ethical Governance: National discourse and civic education should promote ethical leadership, transparency, and accountability as non-negotiable values in public office. Institutional reforms alone will be insufficient without a change in political culture and public expectations.

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